

ISMRRM MiniHub how-to guide

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This document details the main points to consider when planning and delivering a MiniHub for ISMRRM, with examples given from the first ISMRRM MiniHub in Lille, France, held on 13-16 May 2025 (<https://www.ismrm.org/25m/minihub/>). Guidance on inviting the Local Organising Committee and MiniHub Faculty, choosing and using a suitable venue, defining the MiniHub program, providing and supporting sufficient audiovisual capabilities, and publicising the MiniHub is given.

Timeline

Timepoint	Action	Responsible
AD-3m	Appointment LOC	ExCom
AD-2m	First announcement of MH Publicity blast 1 Registration open Program V1 Venue selection Contract with venue	CO CO CO LOC CO/LOC CO
AMPC+1m	Program V2 Publicity blast 2	LOC CO
AMPC+2m	Faculty selection	LOC
MH-2m	Program V2 Publicity blast 3	LOC CO
MH-1w	Signage/Registration Check AV	LOC

m,w,d: month, week, day.

AD = Abstract Deadline; AMPC = Annual Meeting Program Committee meeting; MH = day1 MiniHub. ExCom = ISMRRM Executive Committee; CO = ISMRRM Central Office; LOC = MiniHub Local Organizing Committee.

MiniHub organisers

ISMRRM Central Office

The Central Office is solely responsible for registration. It is responsible for announcing the MiniHub and publicising it. Publicity material can be developed together with the Local Organizing Committee (LOC), but the Central Office is in a unique position to utilise its mailing lists to reach out to potential attendees. The Central Office should keep the LOC informed of the number of registrants, and who has registered. The Central Office informs registrants on what they need to bring to the meeting (laptop, noise cancelling headphones).

If the Central Office is taking financial responsibility, then it needs to conduct all negotiations with the venue that have a cost component and sign the contract with the venue. This will mainly be the room rental, AudioVisual (AV), and any catering. It is important that one member of the Central Office attends the meetings of the LOC to ensure that the plans are compatible with what is available, and to monitor the progress of the LOC.

The Central Office is responsible for providing the LOC with relevant information about the main meeting in a timely manner. This should include early access to the full program and logistical information regarding remote access to the meeting such as which content will be recorded, how the recordings can be accessed and the possibilities for live streaming.

During the MiniHub, the Central Office should identify a contact person from the ISMRRM office for the LOC, and a technical point of contact for potential AV difficulties.

Local Organising Committee

The core members of the LOC should be identified via the ISMRRM Executive Committee well before the first announcement of the MiniHub. The most important element is to have at least one member who is located close to the meeting venue. It is also useful (but not essential) to identify a Chair with an understanding of how ISMRRM works eg (current or previous Board of Trustees member). Given the level of support that can reasonably be expected from Central Office, it is important that all LOC members realise that they are largely responsible for shaping and implementing the MiniHub.

The most important choice that needs to be made is the duration and session times of the MiniHub. As this has financial implications, it needs to be decided jointly with Central Office. The choice will be shaped by the time difference to the main meeting, and the availability of live stream as well as any wishes from the main meeting to have live interaction. This choice

should be made in time for the first announcement. If possible, the location for the MiniHub should be announced at the same time. This gives certainty that the MiniHub will take place, allows attendees to plan their attendance and possibly book accommodation in advance. At this time point, the LOC makes a first version of the program (V1) with the named lectures, and plenary sessions.

Immediately after the Annual Meeting Planning Committee (AMPC) meeting, the LOC gains access to the meeting program (session titles and times). Based on this information the LOC drafts a second program (V2, contains number parallel sessions, session tracks but not titles) that is placed on the ISMRM website and used in publicity. Based on early registrations, the LOC identifies potential faculty members and approaches them. Together with Central Office, it surveys early registrants and the LOC together with the Faculty drafts the final program (V3).

The LOC has to then ensure the smooth functioning of the meeting by checking signage and access, monitoring registration, posters and poster sessions, liaising with local AV and the annual meeting, setting up a dry run with AV. The LOC should ensure that all attendees are welcomed and informed about the meeting. The LOC should be responsive to attendees' wishes.

Faculty/Champions

The LOC appoints Faculty from the early registrants. It may also issue a call for Faculty members when the MiniHub is announced. Faculty should be senior enough to have an overview of one of the tracks of the MiniHub (e.g. Image Reconstruction, fMRI etc.) and to feel comfortable moderating sessions. They are responsible for selecting the sessions from the main meeting program that will be presented at the hub, respecting the timing constraints in the program. For example, if the LOC has allocated five sessions to hardware, then the Faculty member selects the five educational and scientific sessions to be presented. During the meeting, the Faculty member moderates the session and facilitates discussion amongst attendees.

Venue

Capacity and facilities

The maximum number of attendees is agreed in advance by the Excom/Central Office. This sets the requirement for the venue. Before choosing the venue, it is important that it be visited by a member of the organizing committee. Ideally there is in the venue a large

enough room that all attendees can watch the named lectures and plenary sessions together. This can then be loosely partitioned to allow for parallel sessions. For instance, during the ISMRM 25 MiniHub held in Lille, there was one large screen with 6.5 m base used during the plenary session and four smaller screens used during the parallel sessions. There also need to be poster boards for any local poster sessions. In Lille, the meeting room was set up in cabaret format so that attendees were seated in small groups in front of the screens used for the parallel sessions. Chairs could be moved easily between the different groups so that the number of chairs for each parallel session could be easily adjusted. It is important to check that the opening hours of the venue are compatible with the program. The venue must have adequate amenities (restrooms, heating or air conditioning). Required technical equipment is listed below in the section AudioVisual. The accessibility of the venue must comply with disability access standards (ramps, elevators, accessible restrooms). A reception desk is welcome.

Figure 1. Example room layout, based on ISMRM 25 MiniHub in Lille.

Location and transport links

The city should be readily accessible, preferably by high speed train. The MiniHub venue should be accessible by public transport from centres of accommodation and there should

be some restaurants and cafes in the vicinity. It is important that the local environment is welcoming.

Accommodation

There should be a range of accommodation with good access to the venue. These should be publicised on the MiniHub website and potential cost savings sought via Central Office.

Arrival and signage

Central Office should distribute signage and registration material to the LOC member based at the destination city. There must be signage with printed QR codes (see AudioVisual section below) for the tables used for the parallel sessions. The LOC can place the signage and, if necessary, can support the registration of the attendees.

Program

Program overview

V1 of the program should be published as early as possible and inform potential attendees of the dates and timings of each session and information about the Plenary sessions.

V2 should be published soon after the AMPC meeting and include further information about the dates and timings of each session and include the number, length and session type (Plenary or Parallel), as well as proposed breaks and information about any social activities.

The Plenary Sessions can be watched as a group and scheduled throughout the program. Sufficient time within these sessions for discussion is welcomed. The Parallel Sessions require Zoom access and headphones (see AudioVisual section) and need to be distributed across the timetable. The time and date for the Poster session should be chosen and any Live sessions highlighted. The program can then be placed on the ISMRM website and used in publicity.

Programme of events

Lille time	Tuesday, 13 May	Wednesday, 14 May	Thursday, 15 May	Friday, 16 May
08:30-10:00	Registration	No Session	New Horizons	Open-Source Revolution
Break				
10:15-12:15	Mansfield Lecture	Quantum Powered AI	Parallel Session 5	Parallel Session 7
Lunch On Own				
14:15-16:15	Parallel Session 1	Parallel Session 3	Poster Session	Lauterbur Lecture + Feedback
Break				
16:30-18:30	Parallel Session 2	Parallel Session 4	Parallel Session 6	MiniHub Adjourns
18:30-20:30			Lille Social Event	
Break				
22:30-00:30		Sustainability Plenary - LIVE!		

Figure 2. Example of program overview for ISMRM 25 MiniHub in Lille.

Attendee survey

To help tailor the program for the Parallel Sessions to the meeting attendees, it is advised that the MiniHub attendees are surveyed on registration to understand their preferences. Questions can include:

- *What are the top 3 things you hope to get out of the ISMRM MiniHub?*
- *What type of sessions are you most interested in? (Scientific, educational, mix [%])*
- *What specific topics or themes are appealing to you? (Neuro, Cardiovascular, Body etc, [choose top 3])*
- *Do you plan to present a poster at the MiniHub that was accepted for presentation in the Main Meeting ?*

The link for the ISMRM 25 MiniHub survey can be found here:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSce690-CXXh4dh8uzruxRLYwabk-u3RTPsqlcGy_Je_xTDZlQ/viewform?usp=header

Champions

Faculty members, who are not on the LOC, should be chosen as topic **Champions**. They can be allocated a topic (e.g. Neuro, Body, Image Acquisition etc) relevant to their area-of-expertise and requested to suggest talks from the ISMRM Meeting Program for an allocated

number of sessions based on the results of the Attendee Survey. Each Champion is assisted by a LOC member.

The choice should be based on access to a detailed program (ideally the full program from the AMPC meeting, but at least session titles and times). Sessions must be chosen based on the availability of the recording, i.e. ***the session must have already taken place at the Main Meeting when scheduled at the MiniHub.***

Parallel session program

The entire Faculty should then meet and determine the suitability of each of the proposed sessions for the suggested Parallel Session Program. Care should be taken to remove/rearrange sessions in the same time slot where content is determined to be too similar or not relevant to the attendees. The correct balance of Scientific/Educational sessions and Topic types should agree with the results of the Attendee Survey. It should be noted that some Educational sessions last longer than the allocated session time slots and will need to be curated.

Color Key & Filter
Not interested in certain topics? Clicking these boxes will gray-out their header colors below, making it easier to spot your preferred sessions.

- Neuro
- Cardiovascular
- Baby
- Mesodisorders
- Cross-Organ Diffusion
- Transferable Skills
- Image Acquisition & Analysis
- Contrast Mechanisms
- Physics & Engineering
- Primary Sessions & Special Sessions
- Pediatrics
- Preclinical
- AI & Machine Learning
- MR
- Study Groups
- Member-Initiated Sessions
- Gold Corporate Symposia
- Bronze Corporate Symposium
- ISMRM Sessions
- Select All
- Deselect All

Session #	Day	Time	Screen 1	Screen 2	Screen 3	Screen 4	Free table
1	Tues	14:15-16:15	Ed: fMRI from Now to the Future	Sci: AI-Based Real-Time Imaging & Motion-Robust Strategies	Sci: State-of-the-Art Lung MR Imaging I	Sci: Novel Insights in MRI Through Multi- & Micro-Contrast Advances	Spontaneous session
2	Tues	16:30-18:30	Ed: MRI in pregnancy	MIS: Open Innovation in MR from Vendor & Academia Perspective	Ed: Fast & Furious I: Body	Sci: MRI Safety	Poster sessions review
3	Wed	14:15-16:15	Sci: fMRI Acquisition & Contrasts	Sci: Data Pre-Processing	Ed: Harnessing MSK MRI for Clinical Trials	Sci: Emerging Contrasts in Neurofluids	Spontaneous session
4	Wed	16:30-18:30	MIS: Bridging the Gap: Clinical Applications & Unmet Needs in QSM of the Brain	Ed: What Does a Radiologist Actually Do?	Sci: Advanced Body Diffusion: Acquisition & Reconstruction	Sci: High-Field MRI	Poster sessions review
5	Thurs	10:15-12:15	Sci: fMRI Beyond Cortical Grey Matter	Sci: Quantitative Imaging	Sci: Prostate MRI: Emerging Techniques & Clinical Impact	Ed: Contrast Mechanism: Modelling from the Ground Up	Spontaneous session
6	Thurs	16:30-18:30	Sci: AI in AD & Aging	Ed: MRI Data Multi-Site Harmonization	Ed: Why? RADS	Sci: Truly Low-Field MRI	Poster sessions review
7	Fri	10:15-12:15	Sci: Mesoscale fMRI	Sci: Pulse Sequence Design	Ed: MR Artifacts Game Show	Sci: CEST	Highlights session

Figure 3. Example of parallel session program for ISMRM 25 MiniHub in Lille.

Posters

Attendees can be invited to bring along either traditional or electronic posters that have been accepted (and are being presented at) the Main Meeting. A suitable session in the

MiniHub schedule should be allocated and LOC need to be aware of the number and type of posters to expect prior to the MiniHub.

Live sessions

Depending on the time difference between the Main Meeting and the MiniHub, the number of Live Sessions can be determined. Due to the limitations in the number of Parallel Sessions scheduled for the MiniHub (approximately 5), it is advised that Live Sessions are limited even when the time difference is small. This allows for the session moderators to have more control of which talks are watched in each session and for additional discussion to occur within each session. See AudioVisual section for more details about joining the main meeting live.

AudioVisual

To reduce the need for the venue to have multiple rooms and to improve the MiniHub attendee group cohesion, 5 session tables/screens in the same room was determined to be suitable for 50 attendees (ISMRRM 25 MiniHub in Lille). However, this can be adjusted to suit the number of attendees and/or the space available. Each table/screen needs to be equipped with a laptop and a large monitor/screen. Each table/screen needs an associated Zoom breakout room, in which only the audio signal was shared to lower the internet bandwidth requirements.

Attendees join the Zoom meeting via their phones/tablets/laptops using quicklinks or QR code (shared via a slide presented on the large screen used for the Plenary sessions) and they can select between Zoom rooms for each of the screens (e.g. Screens 0-4). This makes it easy to choose and switch between sessions. The video content is only streamed via one laptop linked to one large monitor per table (typically that of the moderator).

Connecting to the meeting

zoom
Workplace

- Download Zoom
- Connect your headphones

<https://tinyurl.com/minihubstart>

Access the whole meeting virtually:

<https://submissions.mirasmart.com/ISMRM2025/Itinerary/Login.aspx>

Login: email address that you registered with

Password: membership number

Parallel session 2

Tues 16:30-18:30

Main screen

Screen 3 Educational Body: Fast & Furious I: Body	Screen 2 MIS: Open Innovation in MR from Vendor & Academia Perspective
Screen 4 Scientific Physics and Engineering: MRI Safety	Screen 1 Educational Cross Organ: MRI in pregnancy

<https://tinyurl.com/minihubsessions>

MiniHub Sessions

Or make your own session
on Screen 0!

Figure 4 Example slides for the Parallel Sessions for ISMRM 25 MiniHub in Lille.

Technical requirements

For 50-100 attendees:

- Good internet and Wifi connection. Wifi must be able to handle twice the attendees number of connections easily, as most users used both laptops and mobile devices to access the internet.

- Approximately 4-5 Monitors, Large screen and hall audio for plenary.
- Approximately 6-7 Tables and sufficient chairs for all attendees. Coffee bar tables and charging station tables are also useful.
- Plenty of sockets and cables, multiple sockets per table.
- Approximately 4-5 Laptops (Personal laptops of the moderators can be used). Ideally with browser extensions like Video Speed Controller to allow the moderators to speed up the videos as appropriate.
- Zoom license and pre-created Zoom Room, linked via QR codes (shared on screen and printed) and tinyurl link: <https://tinyurl.com/minihubsessions>
- An open Googledocs, with all information and quick updates, can be made and shared via a tinyurl links for fast access: <https://tinyurl.com/minihubstart>
- 2-3 wireless hand microphones and hall audio for discussions.
- **Attendees to provide:** mobile device, headphones and Zoom app.

For more attendees, most of the mentioned requirements could be scaled. Wifi scaling is also important to consider.

Alternative ideas: For ISMRM 25 MiniHub silent disco headphones (<https://kopfhoerer-events.de/silent-conference-system>) were investigated. These would not require the attendees to use their own mobile device and headphones, but it was decided that it was expensive and would not scale as easily as the Zoom+headphone solution. During the ISMRM 25 MiniHub in Lille, (Zoom+headphones) solution worked well and only minimal problems occurred. Individual Zoom rooms per table with its own link did not work, as only one room per host is allowed in Zoom. Thus Zoom breakout rooms were chosen.

Staffing requirements

Tables and Zoom connections can be managed by 2 informed organizers (LOC) and an informed moderator (Faculty Champion) . For plenary videos and sound, 1 local technical staff person is sufficient. It is preferable if the local technical staff can communicate in English with the LOC.

During the sessions

An allocated moderator is required to share the visual content via a laptop to the Monitor. The linked audio needs to be shared via the Zoom breakout room. The moderator can pause the session for discussion, move through the session to skip talks, and/or speed up the session using appropriate software.

Live links to main meeting

Due to the lag of the public stream, when joining the main ISMRM meeting live, it is necessary to join directly via a Zoom connection. For that purpose, use one laptop on the stage (using laptop camera and microphone) and wireless microphones in the hall.

Publicity and registration

Announcement to ISMRM community

What we did for the ISMRM 25 MiniHub

- Central Office sent emails marketing the MiniHub to a subset of the membership based in Europe.
- Instagram and LinkedIn were also used.
- LOC predominantly used LinkedIn and gained significant numbers of impressions and shares.
- LOC contacted European ISMRM Chapters to use their email lists. This included British & Irish, Benelux, German and Iberian Chapters.
- LOC contacted senior colleagues directly to spread the word.

Areas for development

- Start advertising earlier. Attendees often make their decision on whether to attend when submitting an abstract. Registration for both the main meeting and MiniHub should be opened at the same time.
- Not all people who are interested in a MiniHub are current ISMRM members. Look for more ways to share outside of the current ISMRM mailing list.
- Find ways to contact former members, based in the region where the meeting is taking place.

The restriction of email communications to a specific geography appears to have missed some people. Multiple adverts about the MiniHub were however received via Instagram, which may have better tools for geographical targeting.

Registration

Registration is facilitated and managed by ISMRM Central Office. The ISMRM 25 MiniHub used the pricing given below:

Attendee Type	Registration Length	Early Fee <i>Before 12 May 2025</i>	Regular Fee <i>After 12 May 2025</i>
ISMRRM Member	4 Days Tue-Fri 13-16 May 2025	US\$655.00	US\$755.00
Non-Member		US\$1040.00	US\$1140.00
ISMRRM Trainee or Emeritus Member		US\$295.00	US\$395.00
Trainee Non-Member		US\$460.00	US\$560.00

Figure 5 Registration pricing for ISMRRM 25 MiniHub in Lille.

Reminders and before you go

Central Office to send regular reminders via email and social media channels to encourage registration.

Information about what the attendees need to bring to the ISMRRM 25 MiniHub needs to be sent via email and shared via the webpage, for example:

<https://www.ismrm.org/25m/minihub/know-before-you-go/>

Post MiniHub survey

It is important to obtain feedback from the MinHub attendees to help understand what works and how to improve for subsequent meetings.

For the ISMRRM 25 post MiniHub survey was advertised heavily on the final day and a majority of attendees responded (~70%). The link for the ISMRRM 25 MiniHub responses can be found here: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/12NTKeQKw4wHSKWJ_nC-NT40Sr7jb0OgCy4UE4DRZh0s/edit#responses

Areas for development

- A suggestion would be to include the question “Would you have attended the main meeting if the MiniHub was not available?”. This question was not in the questionnaire, but it was asked informally at the ISMRM 25 MiniHub with the majority saying they would not have attended the main meeting in these circumstances i.e. the MiniHub is not taking attendees from the main meeting.
- Analyse the responses of the survey and trial different ways of running the MiniHub.

There is a lot to learn and a lot to gain!